

Received: 18 August 2021/ Accepted: 23 August 2021/ Published: 31 August 2021
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5372990>

MoS₂-Carbon black nanocomposite for EMI shielding purpose

Akshita Yadav, Prashant S Alegaonkar*

Department of physics, School of Basic Sciences, Central University of Punjab, Bathinda, 151401, India
*Corresponding author: Prashant S Alegaonkar (prashant.alegaonkar@cup.edu.in)

This work was presented at the International Online Conference on Nano Materials (ICN 2021) held during 9 – 11, April 2021 at Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala, India, 686560

Introduction: Electromagnetic radiations are broadly categorized in the scientific domain of waves and optics. For many years various aspects of EM waves have been studied and once understood it found applications in many sectors since they are particularly medium independent and can be controlled by modulating EM fields. One of the important sectors of applicability is the defense sector where the region of spectrum between the infrared and the microwave has caught attention for detecting any potential threat by tracking, probing, and identifying the nature. These feats can be achieved in several ways but the most important and reliable method is electromagnetic shielding effect via absorption and /or destructive interference. The main motto is to minimize the detection of any device on the enemy's radar by reducing the original cross-section (1). Recently, several reports have been submitted demonstrating and suggesting the design and development of EMI shields using nano-carbons (2) and conducting polymer composites (3), etc. In this paper, the focus has been shifted towards simple carbon inclusions and a nano-composite (CB/MoS₂/CO) made up of 2D-Materials.

Methods: The MoS₂-CB/Cobalt Nano-composite was prepared for EMI shielding Application. The MoS₂ based powdered nano-composite was synthesized by using facile solid-state fabrication using grinding method with the help of mortar-pestle. Different samples (6-18%) were prepared by changing the carbon black content. Characterization of the prepared powdered samples was done by Fourier Transformation Infrared Spectroscopy, UV-Visible Spectroscopy, and conductivity measurements. The constitutive S-parameter measurements were carried out with the help of vector network analyzer (VNA) over a frequency range of 2-18 GHz by converting powdered form samples into toroidal shape samples.

Results & Discussions: The FTIR data analysis shows the prominent changes in the moiety of the samples. These moieties seem to be created by redox-exchange chemical interactions between Mo and Co. Magnitude differences have been observed that led to a conclusion that carbon environment is decisive in exploiting microwave absorption properties. UV spectroscopy over 300-700 nm reveals the contribution of absorption peaks in charge-transfer complexes at high carbon content in composite. In conductivity measurement, the composite shows, low CB content 6, 9, 12% it showed Debye-like behavior, and at higher content 15 and 18%, the performance is observed to be Jonscher-like. In S-parameter analysis, ϵ' is has seen almost flat over 2-18 GHz for CB/MoS₂/Co nano-composite and a systematic change with increasing CB from 6-18%. For 6% composition, ϵ' is 5.2434±0.2321 while it gets double 10.49±0.8188 in 18% composite. SE@interface-1 is almost 95.4% @14 GHz with a bandwidth of 7.9 GHz, and SE@interface-2 is 97.8% @13.5 GHz with a bandwidth of 7.7 GHz.

Conclusions: At higher content i.e. 18% CB/MoS₂/Co showed almost 65% of return loss in microwave absorption characteristics over other compositions with almost 75% power absorption and shielding effectiveness (SE) of 95% over X band frequency these all enhanced return losses making 18% composite more prominent candidate for shield applications.

Keywords: EMI Shielding, Nano-Composites, 2D-Materials, S-Parameters.

References

- [1] Knott, E. F., Shaeffer, J. F., & Tuley, M. T. (2004). Radar Cross Section 2nd edn. (Raleigh, NC: SciTech).
- [2] Acharya, S., Ray, J., Patro, T. U., Alegaonkar, P., & Datar, S. (2018). Microwave absorption properties of reduced graphene oxide strontium hexaferrite/poly (methyl methacrylate) composites. *Nanotechnology*, 29(11), 115605.
- [3] Yao, B., Hong, W., Chen, T., Han, Z., Xu, X., Hu, R., ... & Wang, H. (2020). Highly Stretchable Polymer Composite with Strain-Enhanced Electromagnetic Interference Shielding Effectiveness. *Advanced Materials*, 32(14), 1907499.

